

ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE FAMILY IN AGGRESSIVE SITUATIONS IN ADOLESCENTS

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Abstract. *Aggressive situations that are on the rise among teenagers nowadays, the reasons for their occurrence and origin. The family environment and the mistakes of parents in the process of upbringing in the escalation of aggressive situations.*

Key words: *Adolescent, aggressive, behavior, constructive, destructive, emotion.*

РОЛЬ И ЗНАЧЕНИЕ СЕМЬИ В АГРЕССИВНЫХ СИТУАЦИЯХ У ПОДРОСТКОВ

Аннотация. *Агрессивные ситуации, возникающие в настоящее время среди подростков, причины их возникновения и происхождения. Семейная обстановка и ошибки родителей в процессе воспитания при нагнетании агрессивных ситуаций.*

Ключевые слова: *Подросток, агрессивное, поведение, конструктивное, деструктивное, эмоция.*

The following methods are widely used to diagnose the socio-psychological conditions of aggressive teenagers. In countries such as the USA, Germany, France, Russia, Japan, and Uzbekistan, experts consistently work with mental diagnosis methods.

Aggressive behavior is an inhuman trait based on moral corruption of a person, with an overt negative influence on the inner world of management, aggression, and aimed at derailing it. The formation, strengthening and manifestation of aggressive behavior often occurs in connection with the social environment.

Humanity has been interested in the issue of human behavior and psychological characteristics since ancient times. Many scientists who have conducted research in this field have discovered its extremely complex aspects by researching the study of all phenomena related to the formation of a person from birth. It is known that destructiveness, in turn, is associated with a basic human characteristic such as aggression. In our opinion, aggressive behavior is not a separate type of general behavior, it is directly involved in various forms of behavioral deviations directed at

others or oneself, and requires special research. The entire history of mankind shows that aggression is an integral part of the life of an individual and society. In addition, aggression has a powerful attraction and is contagious - most people, while verbally denying aggression, display it widely in their daily lives. The term "aggression" when translated from the Latin language means "aggression" - "to attack". Currently, the term aggression is used very widely.

When studying by periods, it was found that the greatest tendency to aggression corresponds to the period of adolescence. Aggression is considered as an appropriate way of controlling social situations and events that occur in adolescents. According to G. B. Shoumarov, the fact that adolescence is a difficult and complicated period is connected with many psychological, physiological and social factors. During this period, the essence of all aspects of development: physical, mental, moral, social and so on changes. During this period, serious changes occur in the adolescent's life, psyche, physiological processes of his body, and his social status. In most cases, they have different situations that are opposite to each other.

Common forms of aggression include: conflict, pressure, coercion, bad language, negative evaluation, assault, or physical force. Covert forms of aggression are manifested as avoidance of contact, indifference to the goal of harming someone, self-harm and suicide. Aggressive behavior can be formed when a teenager's freedoms are too limited in the family or when he is given too much freedom. If a teenager is used to the rapid satisfaction of all his needs in the family, he will show an aggressive attitude towards those who hinder his needs in the peer group. Even in cases of emotional denial in the family, teenagers try to draw attention to themselves with aggressive behavior. It is desirable for parents to search for the reason for the changes in the behavior of the teenager based on the constructive solution of the problems that have arisen. If the family members of a teenager have learned to solve their problems on the basis of mutual conflict and shouting, then in another social situation the teenager tends to behave in this way.

One of the most controversial problems is the problem of the influence of mass media on the aggressive behavior of a person. Proponents of the negative effect of social networks and mass media are based on the following information: when people behave aggressively, first of all, when they observe the aggression of others. M. Huysmann and a group of researchers observed the correlation between watching TV shows and aggressiveness for 20 years. They found that the severity of crimes committed by 30-year-olds was matched by the preferences of 8-year-olds. The mechanism of formation of aggressive behavior through social networks and television can have the following form: excessive interest in television shows - aggressive fantasies - comparison of oneself with a character (hero) - aggressive solution of problems and influence on people self-development method - repetition of aggressive movements - use of aggression to solve problems

in interpersonal relationships - support - aggressive habits - underdeveloped social and academic skills - frustration - excessive watching of TV shows, etc. He also emphasizes that the perceptions of conflict identified in teenagers are essentially dependent on family relationships, not only with parents, but also with siblings. So, first of all, he emphasized that the family environment can have a great impact on the psyche of a teenager. When we talked to teenagers, when we asked the question, if someone made you angry at home, how would you behave at school, one schoolgirl answered that I don't have anyone who makes me angry in my house, no one is angry with each other. . It can be seen that the environment in the family has a great impact on the child's psyche. As a result of this, aggression occurs in the child and an aggressive reaction occurs. Changes begin to occur in the character of the teenager.

Self-confidence of a person is not shown in any social activity as in the work of education. Of course, life experience, pedagogical practice and dealings with teenagers help a lot in understanding them. But this does not negate the need for deep study of psychology and pedagogy. To sum up, the study of a teenager involves the solution of three tasks in general: to determine the most favorable features and opportunities for the education and upbringing of a teenager, to evaluate the effectiveness of the tools used in his education and upbringing. At all stages of work with teenagers, these tasks are of different importance for the pedagogue.

Teaching to self-esteem, safety check. Teaching to understand one's own and others' emotions and feelings, improving control of destructive emotions; teaching methods of correcting anger that does not harm oneself and others, teaching constructive reactions in the child's behavior in problematic situations, and eliminating destructive means; consultation of parents with pedagogues (to teach how to determine the equipment that suppresses aggression in children). One of the main ways children learn aggressive behavior is to observe someone else being aggressive. Adolescents who experience violence at home and are themselves victims of violence are prone to aggressive behavior.

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